

A Study on Customer Satisfaction towards Honda Activa with Reference to Coimbatore City

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ABSTRACT

The study assesses the satisfaction level of customers towards Honda Activa bikes. It is based on primary data collected from the respondents using questionnaire. The paper presents the result of a survey of 110 Honda Activa customers in Coimbatore city by adopting convenience sampling method. The researcher has used Percentage analysis for assessing the demographic profile of the respondents, the level of satisfaction of the respondents is analysed using Likert's scaling technique and the reasons for purchasing Honda Activa was analysed using Garret ranking method. The key to generating high customer loyalty is to deliver high customer value.

INTRODUCTION

The two wheeler industry has shown a steady growth over the years. India is the second largest manufacturer of two wheelers in the world. It stands next only to Japan and China in terms of number of two wheelers produced and sold. The customers have a wide choice of brands to select from. In order to survive the competition, the companies have to do a better job of meeting and satisfying customer needs than their competitors. The study has been conducted to identify the reasons for purchasing Honda Activa bikes and to analyse the satisfaction level of customers of Honda Activa bikes.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Customer satisfaction provides an indication of how successful the organization is in providing products and /or services to the market. Organizations need to

retain existing customers while targeting non-customers. So, to retain the customers for a longer time the marketer has to know the customer satisfaction level. There are many types of two wheelers that play an essential role in fulfilling the needs of customers. The customer's needs are more dynamic. Their needs and preferences change as per the current scenario. The development of the two wheeler industry mainly depends on customer's satisfaction. The following questions may arise regarding customer satisfaction. What are the reasons that affect two-wheeler purchasing? What are the features in Honda Activa bike that increases the satisfaction level of customers? To find the solution to these questions, the study has been carried out.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Spreng and Mackoy (1996)¹ in their study "Addressing the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction" suggested that perceived service quality was an antecedent to satisfaction. Although the direction of the quality/satisfaction relationship (i.e. quality leads to satisfaction) is fairly well understood for services, the question of whether or not (and how) this relationship varies depending on particular settings and/or situations is not. Service quality and customer satisfaction do exhibit independence and are indeed different constructs from the customer's point of view.

Duggani Yuvaraju and Durga Rao (2014)² have made a study on, "Customer Satisfaction towards Honda Two Wheelers: A Case Study in Tirupati". The study has

aimed to analyze the customer satisfaction of two wheelers. The study has found that 60 per cent of the respondents have come to know Honda Bikes through Advertisement media, 90 per cent of the respondents were completely satisfied with the mileage and performance of the bike, 73 per cent are satisfied with pick-up of the Honda Bike, 56 per cent of the respondents have attracted by the quality of the service. 50 per cent of the respondents are satisfied with the design of the bike, 54 per cent of the respondents have considered the price of the Honda, 60 per cent of the respondents have felt the explanation were “excellent.” The study has concluded that there is a significant difference among the preferable factors such as, mileage, pickup, price and design.

Williams, et al., (2011)³ in their study, found that customer attitudes have included customer satisfaction, customer value, price perceptions, the quality of the relationship and service quality. Many studies have found strong links between customer attitudes and customer loyalty behaviour. For example, it has commonly been found that higher levels of customer satisfaction lead to higher levels of behavioural intentions, which in turn lead to stronger customer loyalty behaviour, which can be measured through repeat purchases, increased share of wallet, positive word of mouth recommendations, and reduced customer acquisition cost. In other words, there is a very clear and strong relationship between the quality of a product, customer satisfaction and profitability.

D.Vijayalakshmi, et al., (2015)⁴ in their research paper titled, “A study on customer satisfaction of selected branded two wheelers in south Coimbatore” stated that, two-wheelers allow people to navigate roads easily making the daily travel both affordable and convenient. They have also identified that, high

price of two- wheelers leads to dissatisfaction of consumers.

NDTV (2016)⁵ in their article “Honda Activa 3G Looks” described the features of Honda Activa as the scooter that radically remains unchanged wearing the same silhouette. The massive stance of the bike is also retained, this somewhat segregates it from being mistaken as ascooty. The large seat is well cushioned offering great ride experience to the rider as well as pillion. There is enough space for storage under seat and around the foot area of the bike.

Zig Wheels (2017)⁶ in their article “Honda Activa: a detailed review stated that the ride quality is one aspect where the Activa needed improvement. The Honda Activa bike does not address this issue. The Honda Activa bike employs a trailing link suspension at front which results in the handle bar juddering every time, one rides over broken roads and telescopic front forks should have been added.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify the factors influencing consumers to purchase Honda Activa bikes in Coimbatore city.
- To analyse the level of customer satisfaction of the Honda Activa bikes in Coimbatore city.

METHODOLOGY

The study is based on primary data. The study was conducted among Honda Activa customers in Coimbatore city. The sample size of the study is 110. The sample size comprises of different types of consumers using Honda Activa bikes like employees, students, professionals, etc. Convenience sampling technique has been used in this study. The statistical tools used for the analysis of data in this study are percentage analysis, likert’s scaling technique and garret ranking.

DATA ANALYSIS

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Characteristics	Respondents (In Percentage)
Age	18-21 years	34
	21-30 years	32
	31-40 years	22
	Above 40 years	12
Gender	Male	60
	Female	40
Educational Qualification	Higher Secondary	23
	UG	50
	PG	21
	Above PG	6
Monthly Income	Below Rs. 10000	5
	Rs. 10000- Rs. 20000	25
	Rs. 20000 – Rs. 30000	33
	Above Rs. 30000	37
Marital Status	Married	65
	Unmarried	35

Source: Primary data

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. The statistics show that approximately 88% of respondents are below 40 years of age. Most of the respondents are male(60%) and married (65%). Nearly half of the respondents have completed their UG degree (50%) and majority of the respondents earn a monthly income of more than Rs. 10,000 (95%).

Table 2: Reasons for purchasing Honda Activa

S.No	REASONS	TOTAL	MEAN SCORE	RANK
1	To aid my job	7613	69.40	1
2	Availability	6413	58.30	2
3	Colour	5701	52.37	3
4	Price	5697	51.79	4
5	Image	5686	51.69	5
6	Durability	5677	51.61	6
7	Stylish	5431	49.37	7
8	Comfort	5118	46.53	8

* Total Score / No. of respondents

Source: Primary data

Table 2, indicates the ranking of the various reasons for purchasing Honda Activa using Garret ranking method. The reason “to aid my job” ranked first with a mean score of 69.40, followed by “Availability” which ranked second with a mean score of 58.30 and reasons “Stylish” and “Comfort” got the least ranks with a mean score of 49.37 and 46.53 respectively.

Table 3: Level of satisfaction of consumers with regard to the features of Honda Activa bike

S.NO	FEATURES	Total	Mean score	Rank
1	Look or style	462	4.2	1
2	After sales service delivered by the dealer	349	3.77	2
3	Safety Features	369	3.61	3
4	Riding and seating comfort	342	3.44	4
5	Price	397	3.40	5
6	Battery life	415	3.39	6
7	Design	346	3.35	7
8	Availability of spare parts	373	3.17	8
9	Break system	343	3.15	9
10	Storage Space	374	3.12	10
11	Engine Efficiency	378	3.11	11
12	Mileage	342	3.0	12
13	Pick up	322	2.93	13

*Total Score = (SA× 5) + (A ×4) + (NO×3) + (DA×2) + (SDA×1)

**Total Score /No. of respondents

Source: Primary data

Table 3 indicates the ranking of the level of satisfaction using likert's scaling technique. "Look or style" got the first rank with a mean score of 4.22, followed by "after sales service" with a mean score of 3.77. The features "Mileage" and "pick up" got the last ranks 3.00 and 2.93.

FINDINGS

- From the foregone analysis, it is seen that approximately 88% of respondents are below 40 years of age. Most of the respondents are
- Male (60%) and married (65%). Nearly half of the respondents have completed their UG degree (50%) and majority of the respondents earn a monthly income of more than Rs. 10,000 (95%).
- The analysis on the reasons influencing the purchase of Honda Activa bikes using Garret ranking method reveals that the reason "to aid my job" ranked first with a mean score of 69.40 and "Comfort" with a mean score of 46.53 got the last rank.
- The results of the study show that among the various features that influence the level of satisfaction of consumers "Look or style" got the first rank with a mean score of 4.22 and "pick up" got the last rank with a mean score of 2.93.

SUGGESTIONS

Better awareness about the various features available in the Honda Activa bike should be created among its consumers and a proper follow up of activities should be done by the manufacturers in order to identify the varying needs of the consumers.

CONCLUSION

The automobile industry has witnessed a steady growth around the world. With the introduction of new model bikes every year, the Honda Motors Co. Ltd is committed to satisfying the demands of consumers. The Honda Activa bikes are produced in such a way that they are more environment friendly and fuel efficient. This makes the Honda Activa bike a priority in the two-wheeler market.

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